

TABLE—1 EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Cd = 9 μ g ; LiCl = 2M ; HCl = 2M ; 45% TBP in Benzene

Tolerance limit $1 \times 10^3 \mu$ g	Diverse Ions
10	Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Be ²⁺ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , AsO ₄ ³⁻ , SCN ⁻ , EDTA ⁴⁻ , Tart ³⁻ , Malo ²⁻ , C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ , Thiourea
7.5	Cs ⁺ , Rb ⁺ , Al ³⁺
5.0	Ru ³⁺ , Rh ³⁺ , Ir ³⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , Ge ⁴⁺ , TeO ₃ ²⁻ , SeO ₃ ²⁻ , Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ⁴⁻ , F ⁻ , Ascorbate ⁻
2.5	Au ³⁺ , Pd ²⁺ , Pt ⁴⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Os ³⁺ , Sn ²⁺ , WO ₄ ⁻
2.0	Mn ²⁺ , Sn ²⁺ , VO ₃ ⁻ , UO ₂ ²⁺
1.0	Ga ³⁺ , In ³⁺ , Tl ³⁺ , Sc ³⁺ , Zr ⁴⁺ , ReO ₄ ⁻ , Fe ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ³⁺
0.5	Zn ²⁺ , A ⁺⁺

alkali and alkaline earth metals and common complexing anions. Platinum group metals, oxy-anions, bismuth, and chromium were tolerated in the ratio 1 : 500. Gallium, indium, thallium, scandium, and zirconium were tolerated in 1 : 1000 ratio. However, bromide, iodide and dichromate showed strong interference. The tolerance limit of some of the ions were enhanced by selective extraction with mesityl oxide^{6,7} (UO₂²⁺, Fe³⁺), acetylacetone⁸ (Cu²⁺), dimethyl glyoxime⁸ (Ni²⁺) and TBP⁸ (Zn²⁺).

Application to the Analysis of Wood's Metal and Silver Brazing Alloy.

About 0.1 g of the alloy was dissolved in 10 ml of 1 : 1 nitric acid. It was digested on a water bath for half an hour and tin was precipitated as metastannic acid. It was filtered, ignited and weighed as oxide. The filtrate was made up to 100 ml. Then 1 ml of an aliquot was taken and 2 ml each of 25% sodium thiosulphate and 10% citric acid solution were added. The concentration of hydrochloric acid was adjusted to 0.5M. Lead from the aqueous phase was extracted with 0.01M diethylammonium dithiocarbamate in chloroform. The aqueous phase containing cadmium was withdrawn and it was extracted and determined as per the general procedure. The amount of cadmium found was 13.27% and 13.05% as against the reported value of 13.5%.

A sample of silver brazing alloy was dissolved and brought into solution as per the above procedure. An aliquot of 2.5 ml of this solution was taken and was adjusted to pH 5.0 and copper was extracted with pure acetylacetone. The aqueous phase containing silver, cadmium and zinc was carefully withdrawn and zinc was extracted at pH 2-4 in presence of 0.5M sodium thiocyanate with 10 ml of 10% TBP in benzene. From the aqueous phase cadmium was extracted as per the general procedure. Silver remained in the aqueous phase. The amount of cadmium found was 21.18% and 21.58% as against 21.3%.

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Some Organothallium(III) Dithiocarbamates

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It has been recently suggested that the dithiocarbamate moiety acts as a bidentate group in R₃Tl(III)⁴⁺²⁻, RTl(III)³⁻ and Tl(III)⁴⁻ dithiocarbamates (R=Me or Et). We report in this communication the preparation and characterisation of some new arylthallium(III) dithiocarbamates of the formulae R₃Tl(dtc) and RTl(dtc)₂ (R=phenyl or *p*-tolyl), in which the dtc group acts as monodentate and the compounds possess an ester type structure.

Experimental

Sodium diethyl and dimethyl dithiocarbamates were obtained from Alfa Inorganics. Sodium or ammonium salts of phenyl- and benzyl dithiocarbamic acids and that of morpholine-N-carbodithioate were prepared by a reported method⁵. Organothallium halides were prepared through known methods⁶. Typical preparations are given below :

Diphenylthallium(III) diethyldithiocarbamate :

An aqueous solution of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (10 mmole) was added to a suspension of diphenylthallium(III) chloride (10 mmole) in benzene (50 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for two hours and then refluxed for one hour. The two layers were separated. The organic layer after distilling off excess solvent under reduced pressure gave a white crystalline solid, which was washed several times with water and dried. It was recrystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°) and finally dried under vacuum.

NOTES

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL DATA AND RELEVANT INFRARED FREQUENCIES OF SOME ARYLTHALLIUM(III) DITHIOCARBAMATES.

Compound	m.p.°C	Analysis %			Mol. Wt	$\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{C-S})$	$\nu(\text{TI-S})$
		Tl	C	H				
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlSCSNET}_2$	119	40.25 (40.31)	40.28 (40.31)	3.89 (3.95)	493 (506)	1475vs 1462vs	999vs 990vs	356s
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlSCSNMe}_2$	138-140	42.49 (42.68)	37.27 (37.49)	3.31 (3.36)	459 (478)	1495s 1481s	996s 970vs	372vs
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlSCSNBz}_2$	94	32.23 (32.38)	51.27 (51.42)	3.67 (3.90)	608 (630)	1500vs 1490s, sh	992vs 980s	358s
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlSCSNHPh}$	138	38.69 (38.78)	42.99 (43.34)	3.02 (3.04)	518 (526)	1490s 1483s, sh	1000s 970vs	370s
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlSCSNHBz}$	130	37.71 (37.77)	44.22 (44.44)	3.31 (3.33)	523 (540)	1488sh 1481vs	1020vs 1000s	365s
Ph_2TlSCSN	184	39.17 (39.23)	39.13 (39.23)	3.38 (3.46)	507 (520)	1490s 1481vs	1020s 1010sh	370s
$(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{TlSCSNET}_2$	176	37.93 (38.06)	42.37 (42.54)	4.79 (4.85)	520 (536)	1485vs 1460s	1006s 976s	368s
$\text{PhTI}(\text{SCSNET}_2)_2$	150-152	35.23 (35.35)	33.06 (33.27)	4.30 (4.33)	567 (577)	1495s 1485vs	992vs 980vs	370vs
$\text{PhTI}(\text{SCSNHPh})_2$	198	33.01 (33.06)	38.73 (38.89)	2.67 (2.73)	603 (617)	1480s 1470s	1000sh 983vs	370s
$p\text{-tolylTI}(\text{SCSNET}_2)_2$	178	34.21 (34.46)	34.23 (34.46)	4.09 (4.22)	580 (592)	1490vs 1465sh	995vs 985sh	372s

*The calculated values are given in parenthesis below the respective observed values.

Phenylthallium(III) bisdiethyldithiocarbamate :

Phenylthallium(III) dichloride (10 mmole) and sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (20 mmole) in water were thoroughly mixed with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred further for one hour. The yellow solid was filtered washed several times with water, dried and recrystallised from petroleum ether. The other organothallium(III) dithiocarbamates of the general formula $\text{R}_2\text{Tl}(\text{dtc})_2$ were prepared through methods reported earlier⁷.

Results and Discussion

Compounds of the formula $\text{R}_2\text{Tl}(\text{III})\text{dtc}$ are white crystalline solids whereas those of $\text{RTl}(\text{III})\text{dtc}$ are yellow in colour. They are soluble in chloroform, acetone and benzene. Molecular weight determination in freezing benzene and conductance value indicate monomeric and nonelectrolytic behaviour of the compounds. The compounds are insensitive to atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are thermally stable at room temperature but are decomposed on heating above their melting points. The course of thermogravimetric analysis of diphenylthallium is represented below :

This behaviour is similar to that reported by Kupchik *et. al.* for organoantimony compounds⁸.

The characteristic infrared absorptions are presented in the Table-1. The compounds having bidentate R_2NCS_2 group exhibit a single $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and a $\nu(\text{C-S})$ absorptions^{9,10}, whereas those containing monodentate $\text{R}_2\text{NC}(\text{S})\text{S}$ group show doublets for the two modes of vibration^{11,12}. The compounds studied in this investigation exhibit doublets for both the modes of vibration in the region 1536-1450 and 1020-920 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ stretchings respectively, indicating presence of monodentate dithiocarbamate group and an ester type structure of the compounds. This is in contrast to metal dithiocarbamates¹³ of group III where single bands are observed for C-N and C-S absorptions showing bidentate dithiocarbamate moiety. An absorption at $364 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to TI-S stretching mode of vibration, which is in agreement to reported data⁴.

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Complexes of Copper(II) with 2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl) Benzimidazole and Related Ligands

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A survey of literature reveals that studies on the complexes of 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) imidazoline (HOPI_{mz}, Fig.A), 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-benzimidazole (HOPBZ), benzoxazole (HOPBOX) and-benzothiazole (HOPBT), (Fig.B) have been restricted to their analytical applications¹⁻⁶ and effect of coordination on the infrared N-H and C=N vibrations^{6,7} of the ligands.

FIG-A

FIG-B

In continuation of our investigations on the structural aspects of substituted benzimidazole complexes⁸⁻¹⁰, we are reporting here the preparation and the results of spectral and magnetic measurements of copper(II) complexes with HOPI_{mz}, HOPBOX, HOPBZ and HOPBT.

It has been found that the neutral *bis* chelates of copper(II) of the general formula CuL₂ (where HL = HOPI_{mz}, HOPBZ, HOPBOX and HOPBT) are conveniently obtained by refluxing an aqueous methanolic solution of copper(II) acetate with stoichiometric proportion of ligand dissolved in methanol. The colour and physical properties of the complexes with these ligands differ remarkably from each other (Table-1), though all the ligands form six membered chelates with the same disposition of donor atoms (NO). In i.r. spectral studies the disappearance of (-OH) stretching vibrations of the ligands (HOPBZ at 2540, HOPI_{mz} at 2690, HOPBOX at 2280 and HOPBT at 2260 cm⁻¹) is doubtless due to bonding of the ligand through phenolic oxygen by deprotonation. The shift of (C=N) stretching vibrations to lower frequencies in the complexes indicate the bonding of the pyridine nitrogen to copper^{1a}. The complexes are insoluble in water but dissolve slight in DMF, dioxan and pyridine. As expected in DMF solutions, the complexes are non electrolytes.

The effective magnetic moment values of *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato)-imidazoline copper(II) and *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato) benzimidazole copper (II) fall in the range of planar or distorted octahedral copper(II) complexes; while those of *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato) benzoxazole copper(II) and *bis* 2-(*o*-phenolato) benzothiazole copper(II) are similar to common octahedral or tetrahedral copper(II),^{11,12} (Table-1).

The mull electronic absorption spectra of complexes exhibit two or three very intense bands above 25,000 cm⁻¹ (Table-2), probably arising from n-π*, π-π* and charge transfer transitions. It is observed that solid reflectance or mull spectra of some complexes differ appreciably from the solution spectra in dioxan, DMF or pyridine. The energies of bands indicate that these complexes have different structures in solid and solution phases.

The reflectance bands of [Cu(OPImz)₂] located at 17860, 21740(sh) and 23260 cm⁻¹ have higher energies than the octahedral or tetrahedral copper(II) complexes, but fall in the range of planar copper(II) complexes^{13,14}. In DMF, dioxan, or pyridine solutions the d-d band shifts to lower energy and only one broad and medium absorption band is observed

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL RESULTS, COLOUR AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES (AT 308.5°A) OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	% of Cu	% of N	μ_{eff} in B.M.
[Cu(OPImz) ₂]	Dull-Gray	Found : 16.34	14.41	1.89
		Reqd. : 16.46	14.52	
[Cu(OPBZ) ₂]	Brick-Red	Found : 13.01	11.56	1.77
		Reqd. : 13.18	11.62	
[Cu(OPBOX) ₂]	Cream colour	Found : 13.31	5.84	2.07
		Reqd. : 13.13	5.79	
[Cu(OPBT) ₂]	Yellowish-Brown	Found : 12.10	5.31	2.04
		Reqd. : 12.31	5.43	